

Title: How to Send Funds to any GPS Location and Securely Pay for Goods using the Blockchain.

Name: GeoLock-Aid

Affiliation: Human Level Technologies Inc. [www.humanlevel.ai]

INTRODUCTION:

With the advent of modern technology, we are now witnessing worldwide events that have an impact on populations throughout the world and feel helpless in front of so such suffering.

Now, there is a way to help reconstruct devastated areas. We can use the Blockchain to lock a multi-signature wallet to any geolocation and transfer funds to it that will pay for their necessity without relying on any third party.

AIM:

To allow the delivery of goods anywhere in the world and pay suppliers directly after proof-of-delivery has been acknowledged by the system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The application is being tested to secure the proof-of-delivery and allow delegated donors to release funds according to the goods delivered.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain, Fundraising, Bitcoin, Ethereum, Smart Contracts, Computer Vision,

BIOGRAPHY:

Claude started programming in 1982 and now works as a software engineer. As an active member of the Bitcoin community since 2012, he has been studying the Blockchain and has envisioned a way to help people in need of immediate assistance without using any third party.

Two years after starting Human Level Technologies Inc., we are proud to announce the launch of Geolock-Aid in 2018.

We hope that it will help create long lasting connections throughout the world.